

The Tricomplex Polynomial and Its Root Structure

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Abstract:

This paper develops a systematic framework for the study of tricomplex polynomials and their roots within the multicomplex space \mathbb{C}_3 . A complete characterization of root behavior is established, encompassing all possible cases—finitely many roots, no roots, and infinitely many roots. Under the non-singularity condition $\gamma_n \notin \mathbb{O}(i_1, i_2, i_3)$, we show that every tricomplex polynomial factors fully into linear components. Consequently, we prove that a polynomial of degree n in the tricomplex space \mathbb{C}_3 possesses exactly n^4 roots, counted with multiplicities, thereby extending the classical Fundamental Theorem of Algebra to the tricomplex setting. We further identify conditions ensuring that the presence of one root guarantees all of its conjugates as roots. Additionally, the quadratic equation $\zeta^2 = \eta$, for $\eta \in \mathbb{C}_3$, is solved in complete generality, yielding a full classification of tricomplex square roots. These results enhance the structural understanding of polynomial theory in tricomplex algebra and contribute to the broader development of multicomplex analysis.

Keywords: Tricomplex Numbers; Polynomial equations; Roots and conjugates; Quadratic equations; Multicomplex analysis.

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1. Introduction

The progression from complex to bicomplex and then tricomplex numbers extends classical analysis into higher-dimensional commutative algebras. Each extension enriches algebraic geometry and the theory of holomorphic mappings. The tricomplex system $\mathbb{C}_3 = \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2, i_3)$ provides an elegant structure for studying multidimensional analytic functions and polynomial equations. Earlier research (cf. [1]-[8]) examined bicomplex spaces. The tricomplex case, though natural, has received limited systematic study. Here we provide explicit algebraic results, emphasizing root multiplicity and polynomial factorization in \mathbb{C}_3 .

2. Preliminaries

2.1 The Set of Tricomplex Numbers:

The set of **tricomplex numbers** is defined as:

$$\mathbb{C}_3 = \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2, i_3) =$$

$$\{x_1 + i_1x_2 + i_2x_3 + i_3x_4 + i_1i_2x_5 + i_1i_3x_6 + i_2i_3x_7 + i_1i_2i_3x_8 : x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6, x_7, x_8 \in \mathbb{C}_0\}$$

Where $i_1 \neq i_2 \neq i_3$; $i_1^2 = i_2^2 = i_3^2 = -1$, and $i_1i_2 = i_2i_1, i_1i_3 = i_3i_1, i_2i_3 = i_3i_2$.

2.2 Idempotent Representation of $\mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2, i_3)$:

2.2.1 Idempotent Representation of $\mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2, i_3)$ via Its Bicomplex Subalgebras:

(i) The $\mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2)$ – idempotent representation:

The idempotent representation of $\zeta = \xi + i_3 \eta$; $\xi, \eta \in \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2)$, is given by

$$\zeta = \xi + i_3 \eta = (\xi - i_1 \eta)e_2 + (\xi + i_1 \eta)e_2^\dagger = (\xi - i_2 \eta)e_3 + (\xi + i_2 \eta)e_3^\dagger$$

(ii) The $\mathbb{C}(i_1, i_3)$ – idempotent representation:

The idempotent representation of $\zeta = \xi + i_2 \eta$; $\xi, \eta \in \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_3)$, is given by

$$\xi + i_2 \eta = (\xi - i_1 \eta)e_1 + (\xi + i_1 \eta)e_1^\dagger = (\xi - i_3 \eta)e_3 + (\xi + i_3 \eta)e_3^\dagger.$$

(iii) The $\mathbb{C}(i_2, i_3)$ – idempotent representation:

The idempotent representation of $\zeta = \xi + i_1 \eta$; $\xi, \eta \in \mathbb{C}(i_2, i_3)$, is given by

$$\zeta = \xi + i_1 \eta = (\xi - i_2 \eta)e_1 + (\xi + i_2 \eta)e_1^\dagger = (\xi - i_3 \eta)e_2 + (\xi + i_3 \eta)e_2^\dagger.$$

2.2.2 Idempotent Representation of $\mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2, i_3)$ in the form of $\mathbb{C}(i_1); \mathbb{C}(i_2); \mathbb{C}(i_3)$:

Let $\zeta = x_1 + i_1 x_2 + i_2 x_3 + i_3 x_4 + i_1 i_2 x_5 + i_1 i_3 x_6 + i_2 i_3 x_7 + i_1 i_2 i_3 x_8 \in \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2, i_3)$

We define the real and imaginary parts as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} r_1 &= x_1 + x_5 + x_6 - x_7, & s_1 &= x_2 - x_3 - x_4 - x_8 \\ r_2 &= x_1 + x_5 - x_6 + x_7, & s_2 &= x_2 - x_3 + x_4 + x_8 \\ r_3 &= x_1 - x_5 + x_6 + x_7, & s_3 &= x_2 + x_3 - x_4 + x_8 \\ r_4 &= x_1 - x_5 - x_6 - x_7, & s_4 &= x_2 + x_3 + x_4 - x_8 \end{aligned}$$

Each idempotent component behaves as a complex-like entity, consisting of a real part r_k and an imaginary part s_k .

(I) $\mathbb{C}(i_1)$ -idempotent representation:

$$\zeta = (r_1 + i_1 s_1)e_4 + (r_2 + i_1 s_2)e_5 + (r_3 + i_1 s_3)e_6 + (r_4 + i_1 s_4)e_7.$$

(II) $\mathbb{C}(i_2)$ -idempotent representation:

$$\zeta = (r_1 - i_2 s_1)e_4 + (r_2 - i_2 s_2)e_5 + (r_3 + i_2 s_3)e_6 + (r_4 + i_2 s_4)e_7.$$

(III) $\mathbb{C}(i_3)$ -idempotent representation:

$$\zeta = (r_1 - i_3 s_1)e_4 + (r_2 + i_3 s_2)e_5 + (r_3 - i_3 s_3)e_6 + (r_4 + i_3 s_4)e_7.$$

2.3 Conjugations of Tricomplex numbers :

In the **structure of tricomplex numbers**, there exist **seven distinct conjugations**, each corresponding to a specific combination of the imaginary units i_1, i_2 , and i_3 .

Let

$$\zeta = \xi + i_3 \eta, \quad \text{where } \xi, \eta \in \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2).$$

Then the **seven conjugations** of ζ are defined as follows:

(C1) i_1 – Conjugation of Tricomplex Numbers

$$\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1} = \overline{(\xi + i_3 \eta)}_{i_1} = \overline{(\xi)}_{i_1} + i_3 \overline{(\eta)}_{i_1}$$

(C2) i_2 – Conjugation of Tricomplex Numbers

$$\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_2} = \overline{(\xi + i_3 \eta)}_{i_2} = \overline{(\xi)}_{i_2} + i_3 \overline{(\eta)}_{i_2}$$

(C3) i_3 – Conjugation of Tricomplex Numbers

$$\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_3} = \overline{(\xi + i_3 \eta)}_{i_3} = \overline{(\xi)}_{i_3} - i_3 \overline{(\eta)}_{i_3} = \xi - i_3 \eta$$

(C4) $i_1 i_2$ – Conjugation of Tricomplex Numbers

$$\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_2} = \overline{(\xi + i_3 \eta)}_{i_1 i_2} = \overline{(\xi)}_{i_1 i_2} + i_3 \overline{(\eta)}_{i_1 i_2}$$

(C5) $i_1 i_3$ – Conjugation of Tricomplex Numbers

$$\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_3} = \overline{(\xi + i_3 \eta)}_{i_1 i_3} = \overline{(\xi)}_{i_1 i_3} - i_3 \overline{(\eta)}_{i_1 i_3} = \overline{(\xi)}_{i_1} - i_3 \overline{(\eta)}_{i_1}$$

(C6) $i_2 i_3$ – Conjugation of Tricomplex Numbers

$$\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_2 i_3} = \overline{(\xi + i_3 \eta)}_{i_2 i_3} = \overline{(\xi)}_{i_2 i_3} - i_3 \overline{(\eta)}_{i_2 i_3} = \overline{(\xi)}_{i_2} - i_3 \overline{(\eta)}_{i_2}$$

(C7) $i_1 i_2 i_3$ – Conjugation of Tricomplex Numbers

$$\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} = \overline{(\xi + i_3 \eta)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} = \overline{(\xi)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} - i_3 \overline{(\eta)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} = \overline{(\xi)}_{i_1 i_2} - i_3 \overline{(\eta)}_{i_1 i_2}$$

2.4 The Euclidean Norm of Tricomplex Number :

When \mathbb{C}_3 is viewed as a 4-tuple space over the complex field, we may write it equivalently as:

$$\mathbb{C}^4(i_1) = \{(z_1, z_2, z_3, z_4): z_1 + i_2 z_2 + i_3 z_3 + i_2 i_3 z_4 \in \mathbb{C}_3\},$$

$$\mathbb{C}^4(i_2) = \{(w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4): w_1 + i_1 w_2 + i_3 w_3 + i_1 i_3 w_4 \in \mathbb{C}_3\},$$

$$\mathbb{C}^4(i_3) = \{(\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \omega_4): \omega_1 + i_1 \omega_2 + i_3 \omega_3 + i_1 i_3 \omega_4 \in \mathbb{C}_3\},$$

$$\mathbb{C}_0^8 = \{(x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5, x_6, x_7, x_8): x_1 + i_1 x_2 + i_2 x_3 + i_3 x_4 + i_1 i_2 x_5 + i_1 i_3 x_6 + i_2 i_3 x_7 + i_1 i_2 i_3 x_8 \in \mathbb{C}_3\}.$$

Then, the **Euclidean norm** $\|\zeta\|_2$ of a tricomplex number $\zeta \in \mathbb{C}_3$ is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \|\zeta\|_2 &= \sqrt{|z_1|^2 + |z_2|^2 + |z_3|^2 + |z_4|^2} \\ &= \sqrt{|w_1|^2 + |w_2|^2 + |w_3|^2 + |w_4|^2} \\ &= \sqrt{|\omega_1|^2 + |\omega_2|^2 + |\omega_3|^2 + |\omega_4|^2} \\ &= \sqrt{x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2 + x_5^2 + x_6^2 + x_7^2 + x_8^2} \end{aligned}$$

2.4.1 Norm in idempotent form :

Case 1: $\zeta = \xi + i_3\eta, \quad \xi, \eta \in \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2)$

Then,

$$\zeta = (\xi - i_1\eta)e_2 + (\xi + i_1\eta)e_2^\dagger = (\xi - i_2\eta)e_3 + (\xi + i_2\eta)e_3^\dagger.$$

Hence, the Euclidean norms are given by:

$$\|\zeta\|_2 = \sqrt{\frac{\|\xi - i_1\eta\|_1^2 + \|\xi + i_1\eta\|_1^2}{2}} = \sqrt{\frac{\|\xi - i_2\eta\|_1^2 + \|\xi + i_2\eta\|_1^2}{2}}.$$

Case 2: $\zeta = \xi + i_2\eta, \quad \xi, \eta \in \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_3)$

Then,

$$\zeta = (\xi - i_1\eta)e_1 + (\xi + i_1\eta)e_1^\dagger = (\xi - i_3\eta)e_3 + (\xi + i_3\eta)e_3^\dagger.$$

Hence, the Euclidean norms are given by:

$$\|\zeta\|_2 = \sqrt{\frac{\|\xi - i_1\eta\|_1^2 + \|\xi + i_1\eta\|_1^2}{2}} = \sqrt{\frac{\|\xi - i_3\eta\|_1^2 + \|\xi + i_3\eta\|_1^2}{2}}.$$

Case 3: $\zeta = \xi + i_1\eta, \quad \xi, \eta \in \mathbb{C}(i_2, i_3)$

Then,

$$\zeta = (\xi - i_2\eta)e_1 + (\xi + i_2\eta)e_1^\dagger = (\xi - i_3\eta)e_2 + (\xi + i_3\eta)e_2^\dagger.$$

Hence, the Euclidean norms are given by:

$$\|\zeta\|_2 = \sqrt{\frac{\|\xi - i_2\eta\|_1^2 + \|\xi + i_2\eta\|_1^2}{2}} = \sqrt{\frac{\|\xi - i_3\eta\|_1^2 + \|\xi + i_3\eta\|_1^2}{2}}.$$

2.4.2 Norm in Canonical Idempotent Basis :

Case(i) $\zeta = \alpha e_4 + \beta e_5 + \gamma e_6 + \delta e_7, \quad \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \in \mathbb{C}(i_1)$

$$\|\zeta\|_2 = \sqrt{\frac{|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 + |\gamma|^2 + |\delta|^2}{4}}$$

Case(ii) $\zeta = \alpha e_4 + \beta e_5 + \gamma e_6 + \delta e_7, \quad \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \in \mathbb{C}(i_2)$

$$\|\zeta\|_2 = \sqrt{\frac{|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 + |\gamma|^2 + |\delta|^2}{4}}$$

Case(iii) $\zeta = \alpha e_4 + \beta e_5 + \gamma e_6 + \delta e_7, \quad \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \in \mathbb{C}(i_3)$

$$\|\zeta\|_2 = \sqrt{\frac{|\alpha|^2 + |\beta|^2 + |\gamma|^2 + |\delta|^2}{4}}$$

3. Tricomplex Polynomial and Its Idempotent Representations:

A Tricomplex polynomial is a function of the form

$$P(\zeta) = \sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_k \zeta^k$$

where $\gamma_k \in \mathbb{C}_3, k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n$ and ζ is a tricomplex variable.

3.1 Idempotent Representation of Tricomplex Polynomial :

Several idempotent representations exist for expressing tricomplex polynomials. In this section, we consider two important forms: the $\mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2)$ – idempotent representation and $\mathbb{C}(i_1)$ – idempotent representation.

3.1.1 $\mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2)$ – idempotent representation :

Let the tricomplex variable ζ be represented as

$$\zeta = \xi + i_3 \eta; \xi, \eta \in \mathbb{C}(i_1, i_2).$$

Then,

$$\zeta = \xi + i_3 \eta = (\xi - i_1 \eta)e_2 + (\xi + i_1 \eta)e_2^\dagger = (\xi - i_2 \eta)e_3 + (\xi + i_2 \eta)e_3^\dagger.$$

Similarly, for the coefficients

$$\gamma_k = \alpha_k + i_3 \beta_k = (\alpha_k - i_1 \beta_k)e_2 + (\alpha_k + i_1 \beta_k)e_2^\dagger = (\alpha_k - i_2 \beta_k)e_3 + (\alpha_k + i_2 \beta_k)e_3^\dagger.$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_k \zeta^k &= (\alpha_k - i_1 \beta_k)(\xi - i_1 \eta)^k e_2 + (\alpha_k + i_1 \beta_k)(\xi + i_1 \eta)^k e_2^\dagger \\ &= (\alpha_k - i_2 \beta_k)(\xi - i_2 \eta)^k e_3 + (\alpha_k + i_2 \beta_k)(\xi + i_2 \eta)^k e_3^\dagger \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the tricomplex polynomial $P(\zeta)$ can be expressed as

$$P(\zeta) = \left(\sum_{k=0}^n (\alpha_k - i_1 \beta_k)(\xi - i_1 \eta)^k \right) e_2 + \left(\sum_{k=0}^n (\alpha_k + i_1 \beta_k)(\xi + i_1 \eta)^k \right) e_2^\dagger$$

or equivalently,

$$P(\zeta) = \left(\sum_{k=0}^n (\alpha_k - i_2 \beta_k)(\xi - i_2 \eta)^k \right) e_3 + \left(\sum_{k=0}^n (\alpha_k + i_2 \beta_k)(\xi + i_2 \eta)^k \right) e_3^\dagger$$

3.1.2 $\mathbb{C}(i_1)$ – idempotent representation :

Let $\zeta = \zeta_1 e_4 + \zeta_2 e_5 + \zeta_3 e_6 + \zeta_4 e_7$; $\zeta_1, \zeta_2, \zeta_3, \zeta_4 \in \mathbb{C}(i_1)$

and for the coefficients

$$\gamma_k = \gamma_{1,k} e_4 + \gamma_{2,k} e_5 + \gamma_{3,k} e_6 + \gamma_{4,k} e_7, \quad \text{with } \gamma_{j,k} \in \mathbb{C}(i_1), j = 1,2,3,4.$$

Then,

$$\gamma_k \zeta^k = \gamma_{1,k} \zeta_1^k e_4 + \gamma_{2,k} \zeta_2^k e_5 + \gamma_{3,k} \zeta_3^k e_6 + \gamma_{4,k} \zeta_4^k e_7$$

Therefore, the tricomplex polynomial given by

$$P(\zeta) = \sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_k \zeta^k$$

can be expressed as,

$$P(\zeta) = \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_{1,k} \zeta_1^k \right) e_4 + \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_{2,k} \zeta_2^k \right) e_5 + \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_{3,k} \zeta_3^k \right) e_6 + \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_{4,k} \zeta_4^k \right) e_7$$

This can be compactly written as

$$P(\zeta) = P_1(\zeta_1)e_4 + P_2(\zeta_2)e_5 + P_3(\zeta_3) e_6 + P_4(\zeta_4)e_7$$

where $P_1(\zeta_1), P_2(\zeta_2), P_3(\zeta_3)$, and $P_4(\zeta_4)$ are polynomials in $\mathbb{C}(i_1)$.

3.2 Roots of Tricomplex Polynomial:

In this section, we investigate the roots of a Tricomplex polynomial from various perspectives.

Consider the Tricomplex polynomial

$$P(\zeta) = \sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_k \zeta^k,$$

which, in the $\mathbb{C}(i_1)$ –idempotent representation, can be expressed as

$$P(\zeta) = \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_{1,k} \zeta_1^k \right) e_4 + \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_{2,k} \zeta_2^k \right) e_5 + \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_{3,k} \zeta_3^k \right) e_6 + \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_{4,k} \zeta_4^k \right) e_7$$

or equivalently,

$$P(\zeta) = P_1(\zeta_1)e_4 + P_2(\zeta_2)e_5 + P_3(\zeta_3) e_6 + P_4(\zeta_4)e_7$$

where $P_1(\zeta_1), P_2(\zeta_2), P_3(\zeta_3)$, and $P_4(\zeta_4)$ are polynomials in $\mathbb{C}(i_1)$.

Case (1): All Component Polynomials are Non-Constant

Let

$$\deg(P_1) = l_1, \deg(P_2) = l_2, \deg(P_3) = l_3, \deg(P_4) = l_4,$$

Where $1 \leq l_j \leq n, j = 1, 2, 3, 4$.

In this case, the tricomplex polynomial $P(\zeta)$ possesses $l_1 l_2 l_3 l_4$ roots counting multiplicities.

Case (2): At Least One Component Polynomial is Identically Zero

If at least one of the component polynomials $P_j(\zeta_j)$ is identically zero, and the remaining polynomials are of degree k with $1 \leq k \leq n$, then the tricomplex polynomial $P(\zeta)$ admits **infinitely many roots**.

Furthermore, if all $P_j(\zeta_j), j = 1, 2, 3, 4$, are identically zero, then $P(\zeta)$ is the **zero polynomial**, which also has infinitely many roots.

Case (3): Presence of Constant Component Polynomials

If at least one of the component polynomials $P_j(\zeta_j)$ is a **nonzero constant polynomial**, while the others are of degree k with $0 \leq k \leq n$, then the tricomplex polynomial $P(\zeta)$ **has no roots**.

Similarly, if at least one $P_j(\zeta_j)$ is a **nonzero constant polynomial** and any of the others are **identically zero**, $P(\zeta)$ again **admits no roots**.

If $\gamma_n \notin \mathbb{O}(i_1, i_2, i_3)$, the tricomplex polynomial can be determined by its roots i.e. the polynomial can be splits into linear factors. Therefore, we have considered $\gamma_n \notin \mathbb{O}(i_1, i_2, i_3)$, to prove the following theorem.

Theorem 3.1: Let

$$P(\zeta) = \sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_k \zeta^k, \quad \text{with } \gamma_n \notin \mathbb{O}(i_1, i_2, i_3),$$

be a tricomplex polynomial of degree n . Then $P(\zeta)$ has n^4 roots, counting multiplicities.

Proof:

Using the $\mathbb{C}(i_1)$ -idempotent representation, the polynomial $P(\zeta)$ can be written as:

$$P(\zeta) = P_1(\zeta_1)e_4 + P_2(\zeta_2)e_5 + P_3(\zeta_3)e_6 + P_4(\zeta_4)e_7,$$

where each $P_j(\zeta_j)$ is a complex polynomial over $\mathbb{C}(i_1)$, given by:

$$P_j(\zeta_j) = \sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_{j,k} \zeta_j^k, \quad j = 1,2,3,4$$

The condition $\gamma_n \notin \mathbb{O}(i_1, i_2, i_3)$ implies that all four idempotent components of the leading coefficient are non-zero:

$$\gamma_{j,n} \neq 0, \quad j = 1,2,3,4.$$

Thus, each $P_j(\zeta_j)$ is a **non-zero polynomial of degree n** in $\mathbb{C}(i_1)$. By the **Fundamental Theorem of Algebra**, each such polynomial has exactly n roots in $\mathbb{C}(i_1)$, counting multiplicities.

Let:

- $S_1 = \{\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \dots, \alpha_n\}$: multiset of n roots of $P_1(\zeta_1)$,
- $S_2 = \{\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \dots, \beta_n\}$: multiset of n roots of $P_2(\zeta_2)$,
- $S_3 = \{\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3, \dots, \phi_n\}$: multiset of n roots of $P_3(\zeta_3)$,
- $S_4 = \{\psi_1, \psi_2, \psi_3, \dots, \psi_n\}$: multiset of n roots of $P_4(\zeta_4)$.

Then the full multiset of roots of $P(\zeta)$ is:

$$S = S_1 e_4 + S_2 e_5 + S_3 e_6 + S_4 e_7 = \{\alpha_i e_4 + \beta_j e_5 + \phi_k e_6 + \psi_l e_7 : i, j, k, l = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}.$$

There are n^4 such combinations, so $P(\zeta)$ has exactly n^4 roots in the tricomplex number system, counting multiplicities.

□

Theorem 3.2: Let

$$P(\zeta) = \sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_k \zeta^k,$$

be a tricomplex polynomial.

- (i) If $\gamma_k \in \mathbb{C}_0$ for all k ,

then for every root ζ of $P(\zeta)$, the elements

$$\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1}, \overline{(\zeta)}_{i_2}, \overline{(\zeta)}_{i_3}, \overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_2}, \overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_3}, \overline{(\zeta)}_{i_2 i_3} \text{ and } \overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3}$$

are also roots of $P(\zeta)$.

- (ii) If $\gamma_k \in \mathbb{H}(i_1 i_2, i_1 i_3)$ for all k ,

then for every root ζ of $P(\zeta)$, the conjugate $\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3}$ is also a root of $P(\zeta)$.

Proof:

(i) Let

$$P(\zeta) = \sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_k \zeta^k, \quad \gamma_k \in \mathbb{C}_0$$

Since the coefficients γ_k belong to \mathbb{C}_0 , they are invariant under the all respective conjugations. Hence, for each of these conjugations, we have

$$\overline{(P(\zeta))}_{i_1} = P(\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1}), \overline{(P(\zeta))}_{i_2} = P(\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_2}), \overline{(P(\zeta))}_{i_3} = P(\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_3}),$$

and similarly for all combined conjugations:

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{(P(\zeta))}_{i_1 i_2} &= P(\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_2}), \overline{(P(\zeta))}_{i_1 i_3} = P(\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_3}), \\ \overline{(P(\zeta))}_{i_2 i_3} &= P(\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_2 i_3}), \overline{(P(\zeta))}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} = P(\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3}). \end{aligned}$$

Now, if $P(\zeta) = 0$, then applying any of these conjugations yields

$$0 = \overline{(P(\zeta))}_{i_j} = P(\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_j}), \text{ for } j = 1, 2, 3.$$

Thus, each conjugate $\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_j}$ is also a zero of $P(\zeta)$, and similarly for all combined conjugations.

Hence, all seven conjugates listed are also roots of $P(\zeta)$.

(ii) Let

$$P(\zeta) = \sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_k \zeta^k, \quad \gamma_k \in \mathbb{H}(i_1 i_2, i_1 i_3).$$

Since the coefficients γ_k belong to the hypercomplex subalgebra $\mathbb{H}(i_1 i_2, i_1 i_3)$, they are invariant under the conjugation $\overline{(\cdot)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3}$, i.e.,

$$\overline{(\gamma_n)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} = \gamma_n.$$

Therefore,

$$\overline{(P(\zeta))}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} = \sum_{k=0}^n \overline{(\gamma_k)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} \overline{(\zeta^k)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} = \sum_{k=0}^n \gamma_k (\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3})^k = P(\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3}).$$

If $P(\zeta) = 0$, it follows that

$$0 = \overline{(P(\zeta))}_{i_1 i_2 i_3} = P(\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3}).$$

Hence, $\overline{(\zeta)}_{i_1 i_2 i_3}$ is also a root of $P(\zeta)$. □

The solutions $\zeta \in \mathbb{C}_3$ of $\zeta^2 = \eta$ for various values of η are provided by the **Theorems 3.3 to 3.7**

Theorem 3.3: For a given $r \in \mathbb{C}_0$, the equation

$$\zeta^2 = r$$

has **16 distinct solutions** given by

$$\begin{aligned} &\pm\sqrt{r}, \pm i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}, \pm i_1 i_3 \sqrt{r}, \pm i_2 i_3 \sqrt{r}, \pm \frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 + i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3), \pm \frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 - i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3), \\ &\pm \frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 - i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3), \pm \frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 + i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3). \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Let $\zeta^2 = r$

Using idempotent decomposition, we have

$${}^1\zeta^2 e_2 + {}^2\zeta^2 e_2^\dagger = r e_2 + r e_2^\dagger.$$

This implies

$${}^1\zeta^2 = r \text{ and } {}^2\zeta^2 = r.$$

Hence,

$${}^1\zeta = \pm\sqrt{r}, \pm i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r} \text{ and } {}^2\zeta = \pm\sqrt{r}, \pm i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}.$$

Constructing ζ via idempotents:

$$\zeta = {}^1\zeta e_2 + {}^2\zeta e_2^\dagger.$$

Then, explicitly, the 16 solutions are given in the table below:

SN	${}^1\zeta$	${}^2\zeta$	$\zeta = {}^1\zeta e_2 + {}^2\zeta e_2^\dagger$
1	\sqrt{r}	\sqrt{r}	\sqrt{r}
2	\sqrt{r}	$-\sqrt{r}$	$i_1 i_3 \sqrt{r}$
3	\sqrt{r}	$i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$\frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 + i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3)$
4	\sqrt{r}	$-i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$\frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 - i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3)$
5	$-\sqrt{r}$	\sqrt{r}	$-i_1 i_3 \sqrt{r}$
6	$-\sqrt{r}$	$-\sqrt{r}$	$-\sqrt{r}$
7	$-\sqrt{r}$	$i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$-\frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 - i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3)$
8	$-\sqrt{r}$	$-i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$-\frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 + i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3)$
9	$i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	\sqrt{r}	$\frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 + i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3)$
10	$i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$-\sqrt{r}$	$-\frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 - i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3)$
11	$i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$
12	$i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$-i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$-i_2 i_3 \sqrt{r}$
13	$-i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	\sqrt{r}	$\frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 - i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3)$
14	$-i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$-\sqrt{r}$	$-\frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 + i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3)$
15	$-i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$i_2 i_3 \sqrt{r}$
16	$-i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$-i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$	$-i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}$

Note 3.1 :

Case (i) For a given $r \geq 0$, the equation

$$\zeta^2 = r$$

has **16 distinct solutions** in $\mathbb{H}(i_1 i_2, i_1 i_3)$, given by

$$\begin{aligned} &\pm\sqrt{r}, \pm i_1 i_2 \sqrt{r}, \pm i_1 i_3 \sqrt{r}, \pm i_2 i_3 \sqrt{r}, \pm \frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 + i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3), \pm \frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 - i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3), \\ &\pm \frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 - i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3), \pm \frac{\sqrt{r}}{2} (1 + i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3). \end{aligned}$$

Case (ii) For a given $r \geq 0$, the equation

$$\zeta^2 = -r$$

has **16 distinct solutions** given by

$$\begin{aligned} &\pm i_1 \sqrt{r}, \pm i_2 \sqrt{r}, \pm i_3 \sqrt{r}, \pm i_1 i_2 i_3 \sqrt{r}, \pm \frac{i_1 \sqrt{r}}{2} (1 + i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3), \pm \frac{i_1 \sqrt{r}}{2} (1 - i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 \\ &\quad + i_2 i_3), \\ &\pm \frac{i_1 \sqrt{r}}{2} (1 - i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3), \pm \frac{i_1 \sqrt{r}}{2} (1 + i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.4

For a given $ae_4 + be_5 + ce_6 + de_7 \in \mathbb{H}(i_1 i_2, i_1 i_3)$, the equation

$$\zeta^2 = ae_4 + be_5 + ce_6 + de_7$$

has **16 distinct solutions** given by

$$\zeta = \pm\sqrt{a}e_4 \pm \sqrt{b}e_5 \pm \sqrt{c}e_6 \pm \sqrt{d}e_7.$$

Proof:

Write ζ in its $\mathbb{C}(i_1)$ –idempotent decomposition as

$$\zeta = \alpha e_4 + \beta e_5 + \gamma e_6 + \delta e_7, \quad \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \in \mathbb{C}(i_1)$$

Then, by direct computation,

$$\zeta^2 = \alpha^2 e_4 + \beta^2 e_5 + \gamma^2 e_6 + \delta^2 e_7.$$

Given that

$$\zeta^2 = ae_4 + be_5 + ce_6 + de_7,$$

we equate corresponding components to obtain

$$\alpha^2 = a, \beta^2 = b, \gamma^2 = c, \delta^2 = d.$$

Hence,

$$\alpha = \pm\sqrt{a}, \beta = \pm\sqrt{b}, \gamma = \pm\sqrt{c}, \delta = \pm\sqrt{d}.$$

Therefore,

$$\zeta = \pm\sqrt{a}e_4 \pm \sqrt{b}e_5 \pm \sqrt{c}e_6 \pm \sqrt{d}e_7,$$

yielding $2^4 = 16$ distinct solutions.

□

Note 3.2:

If $a, b, c, d \geq 0$, then the equation

$$\zeta^2 = ae_4 + be_5 + ce_6 + de_7$$

has **16 distinct solutions** in $\mathbb{H}(i_1i_2, i_1i_3)$, given by

$$\zeta = \pm\sqrt{a}e_4 \pm \sqrt{b}e_5 \pm \sqrt{c}e_6 \pm \sqrt{d}e_7.$$

Theorem 3.5: For a given $r + i_1s \in \mathbb{C}(i_1), s \neq 0$. The equation

$$\zeta^2 = r + i_1s$$

has **16 distinct solutions** given by

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta = & \pm\omega, \pm i_1i_2\omega, \pm i_1i_3\omega, \pm i_2i_3\omega, \pm \frac{\omega}{2}(1 + i_1i_2 + i_1i_3 + i_2i_3), \pm \frac{\omega}{2}(1 - i_1i_2 - i_1i_3 + i_2i_3), \\ & \pm \frac{\omega}{2}(1 - i_1i_2 + i_1i_3 - i_2i_3), \pm \frac{\omega}{2}(1 + i_1i_2 - i_1i_3 - i_2i_3). \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\omega = \frac{\sqrt{|r + i_1s|}(r + i_1s + |r + i_1s|)}{|r + i_1s + |r + i_1s||}$$

Proof:

Let $\zeta^2 = r + i_1s$. Using the idempotent decomposition:

$${}^1\zeta^2 e_2 + {}^2\zeta^2 e_2^\dagger = (r + i_1s)e_2 + (r + i_1s)e_2^\dagger.$$

This implies

$${}^1\zeta^2 = r + i_1s \text{ and } {}^2\zeta^2 = r + i_1s.$$

Hence,

$${}^1\zeta = \pm\omega, \pm i_1i_2\omega \text{ and } {}^2\zeta = \pm\omega, \pm i_1i_2\omega$$

where

$$\omega = \frac{\sqrt{|r + i_1s|}(r + i_1s + |r + i_1s|)}{|r + i_1s + |r + i_1s||}$$

Constructing ζ via idempotents:

$$\zeta = {}^1\zeta e_1 + {}^2\zeta e_2.$$

Then, explicitly, the 16 solutions are given in the table below:

SN	${}^1\zeta$	${}^2\zeta$	$\zeta = {}^1\zeta e_2 + {}^2\zeta e_2^\dagger$
1	ω	ω	ω
2	ω	$-\omega$	$i_1 i_3 \omega$
3	ω	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$\frac{\omega}{2}(1 + i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3)$
4	ω	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$\frac{\omega}{2}(1 - i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3)$
5	$-\omega$	ω	$-i_1 i_3 \omega$
6	$-\omega$	$-\omega$	$-\omega$
7	$-\omega$	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-\frac{\omega}{2}(1 - i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3)$
8	$-\omega$	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-\frac{\omega}{2}(1 + i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3)$
9	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	ω	$\frac{\omega}{2}(1 + i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3)$
10	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-\omega$	$-\frac{\omega}{2}(1 - i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3)$
11	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$i_1 i_2 \omega$
12	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-i_2 i_3 \omega$
13	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	ω	$\frac{\omega}{2}(1 - i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3)$
14	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-\omega$	$-\frac{\omega}{2}(1 + i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3)$
15	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$i_2 i_3 \omega$
16	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$

□

Theorem 3.6: For a given $\eta = ze_1 + w e_1^\dagger \in \mathbb{C}_2$; $z, w \in \mathbb{C}(i_1), I(z) \neq 0, I(w) \neq 0$, then the equation

$$\zeta^2 = ze_1 + w e_1^\dagger$$

has **16 distinct solutions** given by

$$\zeta = \pm\omega, \pm i_1 i_2 \omega, \pm i_1 i_3 \omega, \pm i_2 i_3 \omega, \pm \frac{\omega}{2}(1 + i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3), \pm \frac{\omega}{2}(1 - i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3),$$

$$\pm \frac{\omega}{2}(1 - i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3), \pm \frac{\omega}{2}(1 + i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3).$$

where

$$\omega = \frac{\sqrt{|z|}(z + |z|)}{|z + |z||} e_1 + \frac{\sqrt{|w|}(w + |w|)}{|w + |w||} e_1^\dagger.$$

Proof:

Let $\zeta^2 = ze_1 + w e_1^\dagger$.

Using the idempotent decomposition:

$${}^1\zeta^2 e_2 + {}^2\zeta^2 e_2^\dagger = (ze_1 + w e_1^\dagger)e_2 + (ze_1 + w e_1^\dagger)e_2^\dagger.$$

This implies

$${}^1\zeta^2 = ze_1 + w e_1^\dagger \text{ and } {}^2\zeta^2 = ze_1 + w e_1^\dagger.$$

Hence,

$${}^1\zeta = \pm\omega, \pm i_1 i_2 \omega \text{ and } {}^2\zeta = \pm\omega, \pm i_1 i_2 \omega.$$

where

$$\omega = \frac{\sqrt{|z|}(z + |z|)}{|z + |z||} e_1 + \frac{\sqrt{|w|}(w + |w|)}{|w + |w||} e_1^\dagger.$$

Constructing ζ via idempotents:

$$\zeta = {}^1\zeta e_1 + {}^2\zeta e_2.$$

Then, explicitly, the 16 solutions are given in the table below:

SN	${}^1\zeta$	${}^2\zeta$	$\zeta = {}^1\zeta e_1 + {}^2\zeta e_2^\dagger$
1	ω	ω	ω
2	ω	$-\omega$	$i_1 i_3 \omega$
3	ω	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$\frac{\omega}{2}(1 + i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3)$
4	ω	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$\frac{\omega}{2}(1 - i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3)$
5	$-\omega$	ω	$-i_1 i_3 \omega$

6	$-\omega$	$-\omega$	$-\omega$
7	$-\omega$	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-\frac{\omega}{2}(1 - i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3)$
8	$-\omega$	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-\frac{\omega}{2}(1 + i_1 i_2 + i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3)$
9	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	ω	$\frac{\omega}{2}(1 + i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3)$
10	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-\omega$	$-\frac{\omega}{2}(1 - i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3)$
11	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$i_1 i_2 \omega$
12	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-i_2 i_3 \omega$
13	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	ω	$\frac{\omega}{2}(1 - i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 + i_2 i_3)$
14	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-\omega$	$-\frac{\omega}{2}(1 + i_1 i_2 - i_1 i_3 - i_2 i_3)$
15	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$i_1 i_2 \omega$	$i_2 i_3 \omega$
16	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$	$-i_1 i_2 \omega$

□

Theorem 3.7

Let

$$\eta = ue_4 + ve_5 + pe_6 + qe_7 \in \mathbb{C}_3, \quad u, v, p, q \in \mathbb{C}(i_1).$$

Assume that each component has a nonzero imaginary part, i.e.

$$I(u) \neq 0, \quad I(v) \neq 0, \quad I(p) \neq 0, \quad I(q) \neq 0.$$

Then the equation

$$\zeta^2 = ue_4 + ve_5 + pe_6 + qe_7$$

has **16 distinct solutions** given by

$$\zeta = \pm \frac{\sqrt{|u|} (u + |u|)}{|u + |u||} e_4 \pm \frac{\sqrt{|v|} (v + |v|)}{|v + |v||} e_5 \pm \frac{\sqrt{|p|} (p + |p|)}{|p + |p||} e_6 \pm \frac{\sqrt{|q|} (q + |q|)}{|q + |q||} e_7.$$

Proof:

Write ζ in its $\mathbb{C}(i_1)$ –idempotent decomposition as

$$\zeta = \alpha e_4 + \beta e_5 + \gamma e_6 + \delta e_7, \quad \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \in \mathbb{C}(i_1)$$

Then, by direct computation,

$$\zeta^2 = \alpha^2 e_4 + \beta^2 e_5 + \gamma^2 e_6 + \delta^2 e_7.$$

Given that

$$\zeta^2 = ue_4 + ve_5 + pe_6 + qe_7,$$

We equate corresponding components to obtain

$$\alpha^2 = u, \quad \beta^2 = v, \quad \gamma^2 = p, \quad \delta^2 = q.$$

Since $I(u) \neq 0$, $I(v) \neq 0$, $I(p) \neq 0$, $I(q) \neq 0$, each of these equations has two distinct complex roots:

$$\alpha = \pm \frac{\sqrt{|u|} (u + |u|)}{|u + |u||}, \beta = \pm \frac{\sqrt{|v|} (v + |v|)}{|v + |v||}, \gamma = \pm \frac{\sqrt{|p|} (p + |p|)}{|p + |p||}, \delta = \pm \frac{\sqrt{|q|} (q + |q|)}{|q + |q||}.$$

Therefore,

$$\zeta = \pm \frac{\sqrt{|u|} (u + |u|)}{|u + |u||} e_4 \pm \frac{\sqrt{|v|} (v + |v|)}{|v + |v||} e_5 \pm \frac{\sqrt{|p|} (p + |p|)}{|p + |p||} e_6 \pm \frac{\sqrt{|q|} (q + |q|)}{|q + |q||} e_7.$$

Since each of the four components admits two independent sign choices, there are $2^4 = 16$ distinct solutions.

□

4. Conclusion

In recent years, the study of higher-dimensional commutative algebras has attracted considerable interest across mathematics and physics. In this work, we have carried out a detailed investigation of the roots of tricomplex polynomials. We established that a polynomial of degree n with a non-singular leading coefficient admits at most n^4 roots, counted with multiplicities, and in this case the polynomial factors completely into linear components. In contrast, when the leading coefficient is singular, a tricomplex polynomial with finitely many roots does not, in general, admit a full linear factorization.

Furthermore, by solving key classes of quadratic equations in tricomplex variables, we have provided a complete characterization of tricomplex square roots. These results contribute to a deeper understanding of polynomial behavior in tricomplex algebra and offer a foundation for further exploration of multicomplex structures.

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